

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>While existing efforts to categorize and catalogue tools for inclusive participation provide a comprehensive view of their adoption and implementation, the rationale behind selecting specific tools or methodologies for urban challenges and their suitability for different planning activities remains unclear. Furthermore, critical questions about the effectiveness and adequacy of these tools in addressing the spatial justice implications of just sustainability transitions are largely unexamined. In this deliverable, we propose an integrated framework to support the selection and assessment of participation tools and methodologies based on their responsiveness to spatial justice dimensions. This framework aims to assist policymakers and planners in choosing the most appropriate citizen engagement approaches to tackle spatial challenges within complex governance structures and promote spatial justice. This responds to the fundamental question of how a just urban transition to sustainability can be planned and managed.</p>			

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Contents

Executive summary.....	7
Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	7
Acronyms.....	9
1 Introduction.....	11
1.1 Purpose and Scope	11
1.2 Document Structure	12
2 Academic literature and catalogues for inclusive participation.....	13
2.1 Academic literature on public participation and citizen engagement: Overview	13
2.2 Catalogue efforts	15
3 Spatial justice and strategic planning in socio-technical transitions.....	16
3.1 The need for a planning-oriented approach in engagement processes	16
3.2 A spatial justice perspective on socio-technical transitions.....	17
3.3 Integrated framework for inclusive planning and design.....	18
4 Tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice within Task 3.4.....	19
4.1 Neutrality Story Maps (VUB/CERTH).....	19
4.2 Community Maps (MfC).....	20
4.3 Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities (DC)	22
4.4 Spatial Justice Package (TUD)	23
5 Tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice outside Task 3.4.....	29
5.1 Storytelling for Participatory Exchange (ISOCARP Institute)	29
5.2 Trainings for Capacity Building (ISOCARP Institute)	30
5.3 Liveable Cities Index (Cetaqua).....	30
5.4 Learning and Action Alliances (ICATALIST).....	31
5.5 Equal Services & Facilities Assessment (LINKS Foundation).....	32
5.6 Transformative Governance Instruments (Adelphi Research)	33
5.7 City Resilience Framework (RCities).....	33
5.8 UP2030 Engagement Toolkit (MfC)	34
6 Synthesis: Strategic Planning Cycle Coverage.....	36
7 Dissemination and Education (TUD)	38
7.1 Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice'	38
7.1.1 General information	38
7.1.2 Themes and Keywords.....	38

7.1.3	Numbers and Geographic Distribution of Participants	39
7.1.4	Publication Plan and Open Access	39
7.1.5	Key Highlights	40
7.1.6	Special Issue on Spatial Justice Tools	40
7.1.7	Policy Brief on Integrating Spatial Justice into Urban Carbon Neutrality	40
8	Conclusion	41
	References	42

Figures

Figure 1: TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle [1].....	17
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Tables

Table 1: Strategic activities supported by Neutrality Story Maps.....	20
Table 2: Strategic activities supported by Community Maps.....	21
Table 3: Strategic activities supported by the CYFUD methodology.....	23
Table 4: Spatial Justice Package and encompassing tools.	26
Table 5: Strategic activities supported by the Spatial Justice Package.	28
Table 6: Strategic activities supported by the Storytelling for Participatory Exchange.	29
Table 7: Strategic activities supported by ISOCARP Trainings for Capacity Building.	30
Table 8: Strategic activities supported by the Liveable Cities Index.	31
Table 9: Strategic activities supported by the Learning and Action Alliances.	32
Table 10: Strategic activities supported by the Equal Services & Facilities Assessment.	32
Table 11: Strategic activities supported by the Transformative Governance Instruments.	33
Table 12: Strategic activities supported by the City Resilience Framework.	34
Table 13: Strategic activities supported by the Engagement Toolkit.....	35
Table 14: Coverage of the Planning Cycle – Tools and methodologies within Task 3.4.	36
Table 15: Coverage of the Planning Cycle – Tools and methodologies outside Task 3.4.	37
Table 16: Number of tools in each step of the Planning Cycle (within and outside Task 3.4).	37

Executive summary

This report delivers the first version of methodologies and digital resources to promote inclusive participation and spatial justice in urban neutrality transitions. Recognizing the interconnected dimensions of spatial justice - distributive, procedural, and recognition - this document aims to support urban planners, policymakers, and designers in integrating spatial justice principles into their spatial planning strategies for carbon neutrality. While the focus is on the progress within Task 3.4 (T3.4) “Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice”, the report also includes additional methodologies and resources available within the UP2030 project for inclusive planning and design. In total, the report covers the nine tools and approaches part of T3.4 and an additional eight tools part of the project that also foster inclusive planning and design. Together, they constitute a comprehensive collection of resources aimed at transforming urban environments into more equitable and just spaces.

T3.4 is dedicated to advancing tools and approaches that foster inclusive participation and promote spatial justice. This task is spearheaded by TU Delft (TUD) and involves contributions from multiple partners, including Mapping for Change (MfC), Design Clips (DC), Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH), Resilient Cities Network (RCities), and I-CATALIST (ICA). The primary goal is to develop, implement, and disseminate tools that ensure inclusive stakeholder participation and promote spatial justice in planning and design processes. The task includes the following tools and approaches (and respective partners): Neutrality Story Maps (VUB/CERTH), Community Maps (MfC), Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth-Friendly Cities (DC/RCities), and a Spatial Justice Package (TUD), which includes several tools and resources. The Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) and the Spatial Justice Package are being developed entirely within UP2030, while Community Maps and the Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth-Friendly Cities are being contextualized and tailored to the needs of UP2030 pilots.

In addition, three foundational activities have been carried out by TUD within T3.4: (1) an in-depth literature review of spatial justice (and related scholarship), which provides the theoretical background for this report and the tools developed by TUD; (2) the development of the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle, which is a conceptual model that describes planning and design activities within a strategic approach and is crucial to understand how existing tools and approaches may facilitate spatial justice in a real-life planning process; and (3) the Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” hosted at TU Delft in November/December 2023, which brought together almost 300 researchers from all over the world working on frameworks, indicators, and benchmarks for the practical application of spatial justice.

Building on these activities, this report combines insights from spatial justice literature (i.e., the three-dimensional framework of distributive, procedural, and recognition justice) and strategic planning (i.e., the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle) to define an integrated framework for inclusive planning and design. This framework is used to systematically describe the tools and methodologies in this report, indicating how they address the three spatial justice dimensions and where they are placed within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle. As a result, the report provides an overview of how UP2030 resources contribute to inclusive planning and spatial justice and which strategic activities they may support.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package (WP) structure. This deliverable received input from D3.1 concerning the description and development status of tools and methods available within UP2030, and from D2.4 concerning the

interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement used for the visioning phase of the project. In particular, the toolkit from D2.4 is considered a resource for promoting stakeholder participation developed within UP2030, which is also described in this report (Section 5.8). It is the toolkit that connects this document to deliverable 5.4 (D5.4), as stakeholder engagement is an important factor for the adoption of financial instruments for spatial interventions. In addition, this deliverable contributes to deliverable D3.2 (second version of D3.1), by providing information on how tools and methods for inclusive participation and spatial justice can be embedded in planning and design processes. Finally, this deliverable provides the first version of deliverable D3.9. The following table summarizes the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content presented here.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D3.1 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 1</p> <p>D2.4 An interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality</p>	<p>D3.2 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 2</p> <p>D5.4 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1</p> <p>D3.9 Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 2</p>

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CERTH	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
CM	Community Maps
CRF	City Resilience Framework
CV	Citizen Voice
CYFUD	Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities
D	Deliverable
DC	Design Clips
DDFV	Delft Design for Values Institute
ES&FA	Equal Services & Facilities Assessment
ET	Engagement Toolkit
IAP2	International Association for Public Participation
ICA	I-CATALIST
JRL	Justice Readiness Level
LCI	Liveable Cities Index
MfC	Mapping for Change
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NSM	Neutrality Story Map
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
SfPE	Storytelling for Participatory Exchange
SJBT	Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool
SJCM	Spatial Justice Conceptual Model
SJH	Spatial Justice Handbook

SJR	Spatial Justice Rubric
T	Task
TfCB	Trainings for Capacity Building
TGI	Transformative Governance Instruments
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TUD	TU Delft
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The present document describes tools and approaches developed and tested during the UP2030 project to foster inclusive participation and spatial justice in planning and design. It primarily focuses on the tools developed within Task 3.4 (T3.4) “Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice”, but it also includes other tools and methods developed in other tasks within the project. These tools and methods comprise a comprehensive collection of instruments for policymakers, planners, governments, and civil society organizations to integrate the concept of spatial justice into practice.

Three foundational activities have been carried out by TU Delft (TUD) within T3.4: (1) an in-depth literature review of spatial justice (and related scholarship), with emphasis on the application of the concept for policymaking and evaluation. This provides the knowledge basis not only for the Spatial Justice Package developed by TUD in the project but also for this document; (2) the development of the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle [1], which is a conceptual model that describes planning and design activities with a strategic approach and has been adopted throughout the entire project to embed UP2030 tools in planning and design processes; and (3) the Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” hosted at TU Delft (Nov 30, Dec 1, and Dec 5, 2023), which brought together almost 300 researchers from all over the world working on frameworks, indicators, and benchmarks for the practical application of spatial justice.

Through the extensive literature review and the symposium, three core dimensions of spatial justice have been identified - distributive, procedural, and recognition. These dimensions of spatial justice encompass key issues of process and outcome and are adopted in the project and in this report as a sufficiently abstract and straightforward way to describe and select inclusive tools to shape policies and urban interventions. In short, justice scholarship offers a conceptual basis for understanding (1) where injustices emerge, (2) which groups of society are ignored and excluded, and (3) which processes exist to include the ignored to reveal and reduce such injustices, and finally to promote democratic values and practices [2]. These three perspectives refer to distributive, recognition, and procedural justice, respectively. A spatial perspective on the three dimensions of justice considers the geographical processes through which injustices are (re)produced, capturing distributive injustices (how benefits and burdens are distributed across space and how space influences such distributions), recognition injustices (how space contributes to oppression and disadvantage of certain groups and how oppression shapes space for the benefit of a privileged minority), and procedural injustice (how space affects decision-making and how decision-making sustains spatial inequalities). These dimensions of spatial justice challenge the dominant neoliberal paradigm in urban governance and decision-making. They are mutually reinforcing and should be addressed together, as inequitable distributions of benefits and burdens, lack of recognition, and limited participation in decisions all work to produce and reinforce injustices and claims for justice [3].

In addition, to understand how existing tools and approaches may facilitate spatial justice in a real-life planning process, TUD developed the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle - a conceptual model of a generic strategic planning cycle consisting of ten generic steps, which is used as a reference for a tool or method in respect to its application in a particular step of the planning process. The Spatial Justice Handbook (see Section 4.4) offers a comprehensive introduction to the topic, clearly explaining the concept of spatial justice and the strategic planning cycle in a simple and practical manner.

The present deliverable covers the seven tools and approaches developed within T3.4 and an additional eight tools that are part of the project and also have the potential to foster inclusive planning and design. It provides an assessment of each tool based on the spatial justice dimensions and the TU Delft Strategic

Planning Cycle. The report then presents the dissemination and education efforts of TUD, along with publications and briefs on the topic of integrating spatial justice.

1.2 Document Structure

Section 1 introduces the purpose, scope, and structure of this report. Section 2 briefly reviews the relevant academic literature and describes existing catalogues for inclusive participation. Section 3 articulates the relevance of a spatial justice perspective on urban transitions and the need to embed tools and methods strategically in planning and design processes, offering an integrated framework to select methodologies and tools for inclusive participation and spatial justice. Sections 4 and 5 describe the tools and approaches within and outside T3.4, including an assessment through the integrated framework described in Section 2. Section 6 presents an overview of how these tools and approaches fit within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle. Finally, Section 7 describes the dissemination efforts directly related to activities within T3.4, and Section 8 concludes the report.

2 Academic literature and catalogues for inclusive participation

2.1 Academic literature on public participation and citizen engagement: Overview

Before proceeding to the literature review, it is important to discuss the lack of clarity and consistency in the terminology used in the field. Terms like engagement, consultation, deliberation, and participation are all employed to describe interactions between individuals, communities, institutions, and/or organizations [4]. In this report, two important terms that stand out in the literature require definition: public participation and citizen engagement.

Public participation is often framed necessarily as a top-down and one-way approach, in which structured processes and methodologies are designed to solicit input, feedback, and contributions from “the public” [4]. As such, public participation typically refers to a broader spectrum of involvement, targeting the various stakeholders and community organizations including individual citizens. Regarding interactions between government institutions and individual citizens, most academic scholarship uses “citizen engagement” and “citizen participation” interchangeably to describe top-down/formal practices of involving citizens in decision-making. This top-down approach requires an active, intentional dialogue between citizens and public decision-makers. In contrast, some scholars and practitioners argue that citizen *participation* is essentially bottom-up and arises from citizens alone in the form of grassroots organization and action [5, 6].

Confusion may arise when noting that *public* participation is a top-down practice while *citizen* participation is bottom-up. Regardless, both top-down and bottom-up practices are widely seen as positive forces in strengthening governance environments, especially from the perspectives of communicative planning [7-9] and networked governance [10].

Given the focus on planning and design practices, which are essentially top-down, this report focuses on top-down practices and covers literature related to “public participation” and “citizen engagement”. Here, the terms “public participation”, “participation”, and “participatory” refer to the top-down involvement of both citizens and other stakeholders in decision-making, while the term “citizen engagement” refers to the top-down involvement of individual citizens only. Bottom-up initiatives from citizens are out of the scope of this report.

Since the late 1960s, there have been various attempts to define and conceptualize public participation and citizen engagement in urban planning. One of the first scholars to embrace this endeavor was Sherry Arnstein. Contemporary to the civil rights movement in the 60s and 70s, Arnstein sees citizen engagement as a categorical term for power, through which the “have-not” citizens can be deliberately included in decision-making processes [11]. Arnstein conceptualizes engagement in a ladder typology with eight levels, in which the first steps of the ladder represent non-participation, tokenism, and manipulation, while the higher levels represent partnerships, delegated power, and citizen control. Through the same critical lenses, Pretty (1995) derived a typology of participation that considers how resources interact with power dynamics [12]. Pretty has identified seven types of citizen engagement, from manipulative participation to self-mobilization. Here, self-mobilization means that people and communities make decisions about the use of resources independently of external institutions, which may or may not challenge existing distributions of wealth and power. In the early 2000s, the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) outlined the Spectrum of Public Participation, which describes five general modes of participation in active tense: inform, consult, involve, collaborate, and empower [13].

While the one-dimensional models described above have been criticized for being too simple to account for the diversity of participatory processes and their goals, their simplicity is not without reason. Arnstein, for example, justifies that the ladder concept helps illustrate the significant gradations of participation.

The model by the IAP2, in turn, provides a general resource for a wide range of users worldwide, including public institutions, private organizations, decision-makers, policymakers, and practitioners.

Scholars have also critically looked at other dimensions of public participation. By considering the diversity of interests within participatory processes, White (1996) identified four major forms of public participation: nominal, instrumental, representative, and transformative [14]. In this typology, the interests of facilitators and participants are distinguished. Two other important typologies are three-dimensional and expressed in a cubic format. The Democracy Cube developed by Fung (2006) represents public participation using three dimensions, namely Authority & Power, Communication & Decision mode, and Participants [15]. The Authority & Power dimension is similar to that employed by Arnstein, whereas the other two highlight the degree of inclusivity and the intensity of communicative exchange among participants. Fung then argues for synergies between public bodies and civil actors, departing from an “either-or” prejudice in local governance and showcasing different forms of participation based not only on power dynamics but on the required level of expertise and forms of interaction. Another cubic framework, the PowerCube Framework, was proposed by Gaventa (2006), which explores power dynamics within participation processes across the three axes of Levels, Spaces, and Forms of Power [16].

A recent advance in the conceptualization of public participation is the 3A³ framework of participation by Hofer and Kaufmann [17]. This multi-dimensional framework presents participation as an emergent phenomenon embedded in planning processes and the wider social, cultural, political, spatial and temporal context. The framework is composed of three dimensions (Actors, Arenas and Aims), each consisting of three interacting elements.

Since citizens are considered part of “the public”, the literature described above can also be used to frame citizen engagement. Yet, academic literature focusing specifically on “citizen engagement” reveals particularities associated with the involvement of individual citizens in decision-making. The conceptual framework proposed by Zarei and Nik-Bakht (2021) delineates four main dimensions of citizen engagement [18]: (1) Engagement Goal, (2) Engagement Domain, (3) Engagement Incentive, and (4) Engagement Platform. The dimension *Incentive*, in particular, offers an additional lens to understand that citizens engage in participatory processes driven by intrinsic or extrinsic motivations, which require consideration of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. With the digitalization of participatory practices, scholars have also attempted to conceptualize digital citizen engagement. Hasler et al. (2017) build on Arnstein’s ladder to conceptualize the relationship between citizens and the data they produce [19]: At the lowest level of the ladder, citizens are passive “receivers” of information. Going up the ladder, as citizens start to participate more actively by indicating their preferences or providing feedback on project/policy proposals, they act as “sensors” and “assessors”. At the highest levels, citizens are present at decision moments and contribute to shaping projects and policies, acting as “contributors”, and ultimately, they submit their own propositions for new policies and/or interventions, acting as “stakeholders”. Other frameworks and typologies have a narrower scope, e.g., focusing on the use of social media for citizen engagement [20, 21].

The academic scholarship briefly described above highlights how complex participation is, making it difficult to delineate what makes public participation and citizen engagement effectively inclusive, as it ultimately depends on the definition/conceptual understanding of participation adopted. For example, a process that increases the power of communities and citizens in the decision-making process is considered effective and inclusive in Arnstein and Pretty’s typology. In contrast, some scholars argue that citizen involvement in some issues (e.g., climate change) should be aimed at social learning rather than at decision power [22] or that citizen power is not always desirable, e.g., when the decision at stake affects a much broader community than that of the participants [23]. Therefore, since the reasons why institutions move toward public participation and citizen engagement are manifold, intertwined, and sometimes conflicting,

there cannot be a single measure of inclusive participation. Participatory processes serve different purposes, and their success should be evaluated based on the different expectations that revolve around their deployment [24]. Dealing with this complexity requires an integrated and systematic approach to participatory planning and design.

2.2 Catalogue efforts

Two catalogues stand out as existing resources relevant to this report. The first is the Database for Participation Methods in Urban Development, which was developed as a pilot tool under the U_CODE project to classify and systematize citizen engagement across participation guidelines from 30 German municipalities [25]. The authors use the spectrum model (IAP2, 2018) to distinguish between different formats of engagement (e.g., City Walk, Online Forum, Participatory Budgeting) and rule-based algorithms to generate engagement workflows based on the initiator of the process, the roles of residents and public actors, and the involvement of super mediators, i.e., third parties such as NGOs that facilitate the process. The second is the Citizen Participation Playbook, which was developed by the CityxExchange Project (Horizon2020) to empower local authorities and communities to become Positive Energy Blocks (PEBs) and Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) by providing a comprehensive framework for citizen engagement [26]. It identifies four citizen participatory processes: Co-creation of Urban Interventions, Collaborative Legislation, Participatory Budgeting, and Citizens' Proposals. Each process includes phases, steps, stakeholders, and outcomes.

While these catalogue efforts contribute to systematizing engagement and allow for clear classification of engagement processes, as in the case of the Participation Playbook [26] and even generating engagement workflows as with the U_CODE project [25], they still lack a consistent embedding in planning and design processes and neglect questions of justice and spatial justice. While the U_CODE project outlines scenarios of planning workflows where engagement may take place, they are based on the guidelines from German municipalities and, thus, highly context-specific. Both catalogues identify relevant planning phases, but these are based on the selected engagement tool (U_CODE) or participatory process (Participation Playbook), limiting the planning context to participation itself. Moreover, the planning context outlined by the Playbook is limited to the participatory process itself and does not consider the posterior evaluation of the implemented results. These two cases leave open the question of what happens with the outcomes of the engagement process in the next planning stage, which is essential for its transparency towards the involved stakeholders.

3 Spatial justice and strategic planning in socio-technical transitions

3.1 The need for a planning-oriented approach in engagement processes

Cities are complex systems, an intricate mixture of nodes, networks, places, and flows, where competing needs, relations, activities, and values coexist and interact [27, 28]. Within these complex environments, diverse interest groups simultaneously collaborate and compete to achieve their objectives. Decision-makers thus require diverse methodologies and tools to capture the diverse needs and aspirations of these groups and address the challenges and conflicts that emerge in this complex environment. An important shift in this direction happened with the introduction of participatory practices in urban planning and design, serving as a conduit for capturing contextual dynamics and local knowledge. While participatory practices are commonly believed to foster a sense of ownership, commitment, responsibility, and social cohesion within communities and among stakeholders, several challenges remain, such as limited and unrepresentative participation, insufficient community influence on decisions, disparities in knowledge levels among stakeholders and more. Most importantly, participatory practices seem to require large investments in time, capacity and management that may compromise efforts to deliver much-needed rapid transformation [29].

More recently, the emergence of digital technologies has revolutionized public participation, transitioning from traditional methods to digital platforms. Scholarly discourse underscores the role of technology in fostering citizen engagement and democratizing decision-making processes. In particular, digital public participation tools and platforms can streamline stakeholder involvement, overcoming constraints of time, space, and participation capacity associated with traditional methods. However, challenges and criticisms accompany digital participation. Issues such as audience size, sampling methods, bias, and data accuracy affect the quantity and quality of engagement; the digital divide, training needs, costs, and socio-political context further complicates implementation [30-32].

Although various innovative tools and methods have been developed to facilitate and improve citizen and community engagement, these efforts remain largely disconnected from urban planning and design processes in practice. This disconnection is problematic because different planning and design activities require tailored tools and methods for addressing not only specific local problems but also the needs of people who will use them (both facilitators and participants). Without a deliberate emphasis on planning and design processes, many opportunities for meaningful and effective engagement are lost, and the potential of participation tools for inclusive decision-making remains underutilized.

To systematize the application of participation tools and methods within local planning processes and clarify how they foster inclusive planning and design, TUD developed within UP2030 the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Figure 1) [1]. Embedded within the Dutch tradition of visioning and strategic planning, which emphasizes the integration of policy and design alongside a robust participatory ethos, the cycle is a conceptual model that incorporates public participation and stakeholder engagement in planning through an iterative series of steps, including identifying needs, engaging stakeholders, visioning, designing strategies, evaluating feasibility and impact, designing policies, designing interventions, implementing and testing, evaluating, and scaling up. The model illustrates how each of these steps presents opportunities for engagement, including citizens and other local actors. The model considers

design as an integral part of strategic planning, thus encompassing both planning and design (in line with the UP2030 goals).

Figure 1: TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle [1].

3.2 A spatial justice perspective on socio-technical transitions

In response to more frequent and severe climate impacts in urban areas, cities are at the forefront of socio-technical transitions. Cities worldwide have developed transition strategies and are pursuing ambitious goals across multiple sectors to become smart, sustainable, circular, and/or resilient. These strategies have often materialized in infrastructure-based interventions across different scales, from the often-subsided adoption of solar panels and electric cars to the large-scale implementation of green-blue infrastructure and nature-based solutions.

In a highly complex and unequal space such as the city, climate-related urban interventions have a profound impact on the livelihoods of individuals and communities, from daily disruptions to long-term infrastructure lock-ins that perpetuate inequality across the city. Inequalities also emerge when the interventions fail to achieve their intended goals and/or create adverse effects elsewhere. The failure of

adaptation measures, particularly, is referred to as maladaptation, a term that has become common in climate reports. Examining maladaptation from an urban perspective reveals that poorly planned infrastructure projects (e.g., green spaces) can lead to gentrification and the displacement of certain social groups or significantly impact the well-being and sense of community of those who remain.

In this context, a spatial justice perspective calls for a critical reflection on:

- the distributive dimension of socio-technical transitions: who has access to the benefits and who carries the burdens of socio-technical transitions.
- the procedural dimension: the level of transparency and responsiveness of spatial governance, engagement of residents in transition decision-making.
- the recognition dimension: recognizing vulnerable social groups and their intersectional needs, aspirations and trajectories in the planning and implementation of socio-technical transitions.

As the way socio-technical transitions unfold determines our ability to address existing and prevent future inequalities in our society, it is essential to understand how planning and design can be used to promote just and inclusive transitions.

3.3 Integrated framework for inclusive planning and design

By combining the three dimensions of spatial justice and the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle, this report offers a foundational framework for inclusive planning and design that can support local governments in pursuing their strategic goals and leaving no one behind¹. The framework is used in the subsequent sections to describe and assess UP2030 tools and methods based on how they address the three dimensions of spatial justice (distributive, recognition, procedural) and identify stages in the planning and design process where such tools and methods can be applied to engage citizens, communities, and other urban actors.

¹ See the “Handbook on Spatial Justice” for more information on spatial justice in planning [33].

4 Tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice within Task 3.4

T3.4 specifically aims to develop tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice. In addition, the task promotes their integration into planning and design processes to ensure their potential is fulfilled in practice. The task includes the following tools and approaches (and respective partners): Neutrality Story Maps (VUB/CERTH), Community Maps (MfC), Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth-Friendly Cities (DC/RCities), and Spatial Justice Package (TUD). The Neutrality Story Maps and the Spatial Justice Package are being developed entirely within UP2030, while Community Maps and the Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth-Friendly Cities entered the project already developed and are being contextualized and tailored to the needs of UP2030 pilot cities.

In the following sections, these tools and approaches are described.

4.1 Neutrality Story Maps (VUB/CERTH)

Description

Neutrality Story Maps is a communication tool being developed by Vrije Universiteit Brussels (VUB) that allows citizens and policymakers to explore different ways of engaging in climate neutrality-related issues. Using digital storytelling and future scenarios, Neutrality Story Maps allow sharing experiences, issues, concerns, hopes and needs regarding climate and sustainability in the city and empower citizens to communicate their lived experience and future vision of their city in a narrative format. In particular, the use of storytelling lowers the threshold for participation, helping to include citizens that are often not engaged in local governance processes. By allowing for a two-way communication stream that encourages citizen participation in urban planning, the tool promotes anticipatory instead of reactive governance and fosters trust between residents and the public sector.

The Neutrality Story Maps methodology is under development within UP2030 in a co-creative process to foster tool ownership in each pilot city. Two rounds of development are planned, starting with Thessaloniki, Milan, and Muenster. The other cities will follow in the second round of co-design. The mock-up from the first round will be presented at the UP2030 Cities Knowledge Exchange Event in Rotterdam in June 2024. Based on the feedback gathered on the mock-ups, the first version of the tool will be coded by CERTH between June and September 2024, with the first version of the tool expected by September 2024 (although not all features will be present or final). The second round of co-design will include the other UP2030 cities and further develop, refine, and align the first version of the tool with the needs of all pilot cities. The climate stories will then be created using the tool by the end of the project.

Analysis

Spatial Justice Dimensions

Neutrality Story Maps amplifies the voices of vulnerable groups and, by centering their lived experiences in urban adaptation planning, it contributes to the recognition justice dimension. Through a collaborative co-design process, city stakeholders are actively involved and empowered in developing the maps, fostering inclusivity and procedural justice. The tool also addresses distributive justice by unveiling the concerns and hopes of marginalized communities, potentially leading to more equitable resource

distribution and policy outcomes. However, its effectiveness in this regard relies on political will and the translation of digital stories into actionable policies.

Strategic Planning Cycle

In the strategic planning cycle, Neutrality Story Maps addresses the first steps (Table 1). The two main features of this tool – storytelling and future scenarios – contribute to a nuanced understanding of local needs and issues (step 1), actively involve stakeholders (step 2), facilitate collective envisioning of future scenarios (step 3), and enable stakeholders to co-create shared visions and strategies for climate neutrality (step 4). In the late stages of the cycle, Neutrality Story maps can also be used to evaluate and monitor the impact of specific interventions on people’s lives (step 9) and support communicative efforts to upscale them (step 10).

Table 1: Strategic activities supported by Neutrality Story Maps.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	x
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	
Co-design Interventions	
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	x
Upscale	x

Challenges and opportunities

While digital tools entail additional challenges for stakeholder and citizen engagement, such as the digital divide, data accuracy and reliability, and the potential misuse of data by various stakeholders, the co-creative design approach employed by VUB helps to ensure ownership by municipalities and, consequently, their responsible use of the tool. In addition, the use of storytelling provides a citizen-friendly way of engagement, which mitigates the digital divide challenge. Their co-creative approach is also in line with the UP2030 for inclusive planning and design processes.

4.2 Community Maps (MfC)

Description

Community Maps is a tool by Mapping for Change (MfC) to develop digital representations of physical space through participatory action through a responsive, mobile-friendly web application specifically designed for participatory mapping. It provides a map-based interface to create, edit and visualize geographic information. By centering discussions around maps, the application allows for public or private contributions to encourage conversation about local places and topics and convey strong messages in a more impactful way than words.

Community Maps has been utilized in multiple contexts over the past 15 years and entered the project at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 9. Within UP2030, MfC is currently working with Budapest and Belfast. With Budapest, there was the need to translate the platform interface into the local language, which was not previously available. The tool will be available in Hungarian by September 2024. With Belfast, the tool will be used to visualize data on climate risks and related projects in the city, alongside other datasets still to be defined.

Analysis

Spatial Justice Dimensions

Community Maps is a participatory mapping tool designed to involve citizens in decision-making by enabling them to create, edit, and visualize geographic information through a mobile-friendly web application. This tool promotes recognition justice by providing a neutral medium for underrepresented groups to make their needs and vulnerabilities visible and fostering a sense of ownership over their contributions. It also supports procedural justice by ensuring broad public participation in an open and transparent process, thereby building trust and informing decision-making with diverse perspectives. Through mapping, the tool helps reveal inequities in the distribution of public goods, economic opportunities, and healthy environments, facilitating discussions on how to address and redistribute urban resources.

Strategic Planning Cycle

Community Maps can be used to support several steps throughout the planning cycle (Table 2). By enabling the integration of community input, Community Maps primarily contribute to the identification of local needs and issues while engaging communities and individual citizens as key stakeholders at the very beginning of the cycle (steps 1 and 2). Community input is crucial for developing visions, strategies, policies, and interventions that address the real and local needs of people (steps 2, 3, 6, and 7). Community maps can also help evaluate and monitor the process of policy and design interventions by following up with communities.

Table 2: Strategic activities supported by Community Maps.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	x
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	x
Upscale	

Challenges and opportunities

While digital tools entail additional challenges for stakeholder and citizen engagement, such as the digital divide, data accuracy and reliability, and potential data misuse by various stakeholders, the participation action approach employed by MfC ensures an inclusive, rigorous, and transparent use of Community Maps. Their approach is also in line with the UP2030 proposition to embed tools and methods – digital or otherwise – in planning and design processes to ensure that community input effectively influences decision-making.

4.3 Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities (DC)

Description

The Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities (CYFUD) developed by Design Clips (DC) is a comprehensive approach that integrates existing public participation frameworks with tailored activities specifically designed for children and youth. The methodology uses existing validated guidelines and frameworks for public participation as a baseline and advances them by broadening the frameworks to the characteristics and needs of children and youth. The methodology takes into consideration the needs and aspirations of these groups in planning processes by (1) designing tailored participatory activities that are aligned with their interests, capabilities and concerns and (2) translating the harvested insights into design solutions, particularly small-scale interventions in city public spaces that focus on spatial quality enhancement tailored to the needs of young citizens as equal users of the city.

In UP2030, the methodology developed by DC needs to be tailored to the characteristics of two pilot cities - Budapest and Belfast. Preliminary meetings have already happened, and DC expects to receive detailed information about the project site and scope from the cities by June 2024. With this, DC will tailor and deliver the methodology and accompanying materials by mid-September 2024, allowing the cities to leverage the school calendar to start participatory activities.

Analysis

Spatial Justice Dimensions

The CYFUD methodology contributes to the recognition justice dimension by acknowledging the importance of including the voices of children and youth in urban planning and design processes and giving them a platform to express their needs and preferences. By actively involving children in decision-making, the tool opens a democratic process to those who are often excluded from elections and voting based on age. The method employs alternative means for communication (e.g. arts, experiential learning) to design a range of interactive activities based on the target group's characteristics (knowledge, interests, scale, etc.) to ensure their genuine interest and full understanding of the process. The approach shapes the redistribution of benefits based on the needs of the younger population, anticipating future demands from the urban space and therefore improving the responsiveness of local governance.

Strategic Planning Cycle

The CYFUD methodology can be used to support several steps in the planning cycle (Table 3). It provides additional insights on the needs of children and youth (step 1). By using means of communication accessible to children and youth, this approach helps in reaching a commonly overlooked audience (step 2) and formulating their needs into collective visions and strategy (step 3 and 4). Given the focus on urban

design, CYFUD specially addresses the step of co-designing interventions (step 5). The CYFUD embodies methods of co-designing spatial policy (step 6), empowering the young to actively participate in public discourses to shape their cities. In the context of tactical urbanism, the method also allows for testing urban interventions (step 8). Special attention is given to the replication of the approach by promoting capacity building within Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and municipalities (step 10).

Table 3: Strategic activities supported by the CYFUD methodology.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	x
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	x
Evaluate	
Upscale	x

Challenges and opportunities

A potential challenge is to effectively translate the insights gathered from children and the youth into actionable design solutions. The approach promoted by DC helps to address this challenge: by tailoring the methodology to the local context and by supporting capacity building within the municipality, their approach helps to connect the methodology to the existing processes in the city and capacitates city officials to understand the data collected, facilitating the translation of inputs from younger generations into actionable action. Their approach is also in line with UP2030 proposition for contextual and inclusive planning and design processes.

4.4 [Spatial Justice Package \(TUD\)](#)

Description

To foster spatial justice in planning and design processes, TUD is developing a dedicated Spatial Justice Package, encompassing six products tailored for specific users/audiences. They are described below and summarized in

Table 4.

1. Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (3 Dimensions, 9 components)

The Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM) is based on an extensive literature review at the intersection of justice, spatial justice, and planning. The SJCM conceptualizes Spatial Justice by defining applicable components and goals for each justice dimension (Recognition, Procedural, and Distributive). When approached as an analytical framework, it allows for a structured and comprehensive way of assessing how aspects of spatial justice are considered in planning and design while drawing attention to the underlying components that build each dimension. In UP2030, the SJCM serves as a foundation for the development of tools 2-5.

2. Spatial Justice Rubric

The Spatial Justice Rubric (SJR) is a set of qualitative benchmarks to promote the consistent application of justice values and just standards in urban planning and in broader aspects of governance (policy, programs, projects, reports, etc.). To articulate and assess the components devised in the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM), it provides criteria with further explanation and examples. It can be used as a playbook or for self-assessment tool, containing guidelines and recommendations for practice or public policy.

3. Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool

The Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT) is a qualitative evaluation tool designed to measure the application of justice considerations in urban governance and planning of a city or region. It provides a score by assigning levels of justice of their attainment against the highlighted components of the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model and visualizations in a dashboard that assist the reflection and improvement of processes (and outcomes) towards spatial justice.

4. Justice Readiness Level

Justice Readiness Levels (JRL) is a complementary visual tool to monitor, visualize, and compare how justice is considered in decision-making. It aims to provide a shared understanding of justice considerations across many aspects of urban planning and design. Inspired by the TRL method, the JRL provides a standard language that can be used across disciplines and organizations to better communicate and assess justice.

5. Spatial Justice Handbook

The Spatial Justice Handbook (SJH) is designed for urban planners, policymakers, activists, community leaders, academics, and students interested in integrating principles of justice into spatial planning and urban development. It is a comprehensive guide for those seeking to understand and apply spatial justice concepts to create equitable and inclusive urban spaces. It also describes tools, methods, strategies, and insights to address distributive, procedural and recognition justice in spatial planning. Organized into five sections, it begins with introducing the concepts of spatial, distributive, procedural, and recognition justice, laying the theoretical groundwork. The second part addresses strategies for implementing spatial justice. Here, there is a focus on participatory planning methods, strategies for equitable resource distribution, and approaches to enhancing inclusivity and diversity in urban spaces. Next, part three of the handbook delves into tools and techniques for monitoring and benchmarking spatial justice; part four tackles the challenges and future directions in the spatial justice discussion; and part five takes a step back and reflects on the ethical dimensions of spatial justice, the role of planners, and the moral imperative of leaving no one behind. The Handbook then ends with a call to action. This structure ensures that readers gain a holistic understanding of spatial justice and are equipped with both the theoretical insights and practical tools needed to enact meaningful change.

6. Citizen Voice

Citizen Voice (CV) is a digital spatial survey tool for public participation and citizen engagement in urban decision-making processes. The tool gathers both quantitative and qualitative data, thus addressing the need to understand citizens' lived experiences and subjective experiences in the city. As such, it aims to foster effective, sustainable, and inclusive participation while ensuring functional utility and flexibility in engagement arrangements.

Table 4: Spatial Justice Package and encompassing tools.

	Name	Type	Format	Short description	Audience
1	Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM)	Visual + text	PDF	A conceptual diagram accompanied by the description of spatial justice dimensions and associated components.	Academia / Practice
2	Spatial Justice Rubric (SJR)	Text	PDF	Qualitative rubric with a list of spatial justice criteria, accompanied by guidelines (how to use).	Practice
3	Justice Readiness Level (JRL)	Visual	PDF	Benchmarking system used to monitor progress, visualize and compare the level of justice considerations.	Practice
4	Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT)	Tool	Excel	Evaluation tool (dashboard) designed to benchmark justice considerations.	Practice
5	Spatial Justice Handbook	Text	PDF	The Spatial Justice Handbook is a comprehensive guide to support the application of Spatial Justice in urban research and practice.	Academia/ Practice
6	Citizen Voice	Digital tool	GitHub repository	Digital survey tool to collect spatial information from local stakeholders and citizens.	Academia/ Practice

Analysis

Spatial Justice Dimensions

The Spatial Justice Package serves as an overarching product, guiding other designs, policies, and interventions in integrating the individual components of spatial justice and promoting inclusive planning. Within the package, tools 1 to 5 serve primarily the procedural and distributive dimensions, guiding planning from a governance perspective, while tool 6 contributes to the recognition justice dimension by enabling the collection of qualitative (subjective) data from citizens and other local stakeholders about their living environment.

Strategic Planning Cycle

The connections of all tools within the Spatial Justice Package are presented in

Table 5. As a conceptual model, the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (tool 1) mostly supports steps 1 and 10, providing a comprehensive overview of spatial justice in planning and design. The Spatial Justice Rubric, the Spatial Justice Readiness Level, and the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (tools 2 to 4) are oriented towards practice, supporting primarily the identification of local needs and issues through the lenses of spatial justice (step 1), the engagement of stakeholders in justice questions related to the built environment (step 2), the co-design of strategies and policies that are sensitive to spatial justice considerations (step 6), and the evaluation of interventions from a spatial justice perspective (step 9). The Spatial Justice Handbook is a capacity-building resource and, thus, supports step 10. In the strategic planning cycle, Citizen Voice (tool 6) acts like Community Maps and supports steps 1 to 4, 6, 7, and 9.

Table 5: Strategic activities supported by the Spatial Justice Package.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	Spatial Justice Package					
	Tool 1	Tool 2	Tool 3	Tool 4	Tool 5	Tool 6
Identify Needs	X	X	X	X		X
Engage Stakeholders		X	X	X		X
Envision Together						X
Co-design Strategies		X	X	X		X
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility						
Co-design Policies		X	X	X		X
Co-design Interventions						X
Implement and Test Prototypes						
Evaluate		X	X	X		X
Upscale	X				X	

Challenges and opportunities

The Spatial Justice Package targets both academia and practice. The main challenge with applying the Spatial Justice Package, particularly tools 2-4 that target practice, is inherent to the challenge of addressing justice itself, which touches upon the ethical, moral, and political issues that arise in the pursuit of equitable urban development. These challenges often involve differing opinions on what constitutes fairness, justice, and the common good. Being a digital tool, Citizen Voice (tool 6) faces issues similar to those of Neutrality Story Maps and Community Maps. Here, the issues are mitigated by grounding the application of this tool in the spatial justice principles provided by the other tools in the package.

5 Tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice outside Task 3.4

This section describes tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice developed outside T3.4. For this reason, the analysis in this section is limited to the positioning of the tools within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle.

5.1 Storytelling for Participatory Exchange (ISOCARP Institute)

Description

The Storytelling methodology, developed by the ISOCARP Institute, facilitates co-exchange of knowledge, ideas, experiences, and obstacles among stakeholders through storytelling. This method encourages individuals to communicate affectively rather than cognitively, reducing conflict and fostering productive, intersectional co-learning. The process includes capacity-building activities and workshops, teaching the fundamentals of storytelling for urban planning and decision-making. It aims to create neutral spaces for idea exchange, level participation voices, and increase accessibility for marginalized perspectives. With an understanding of storytelling as a tool, municipalities can better understand different forms of knowledge and perspectives. This allows for more informed and inclusive decision-making in urban planning. The tool is a novel form of participatory data collection. It is accessible, easy to use and encourages creativity in participatory planning discussions, enabling citizens to become active participants whose experiences, perspectives, and opinions help bridge the gap between local knowledge and planning strategies.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

Similar to the Neutrality Story Maps, the Storytelling for Participatory Exchange (SfPE) provided by ISOCARP supports steps 1 to 5 at the beginning of the strategic planning cycle and steps 9-10 at the end. In addition, because of the focus on urban planning, the tool also contributes to involving stakeholders in co-designing spatial inventions (step 7).

Table 6: Strategic activities supported by the Storytelling for Participatory Exchange.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	x
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	x
Co-design Policies	
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	x
Upscale	x

5.2 Trainings for Capacity Building (ISOCARP Institute)

Description

The ISOCARP Trainings for Capacity Building (TfCB), developed by the ISOCARP Institute, cover diverse topics related to sustainable urban planning. The trainings are tailored to local contexts, addressing organizational gaps in knowledge and skills related to urban planning and sustainability, and enable the participants, specifically the leadership and employees of urban municipalities, to carry out future-proof sustainable urban planning in their respective cities. The comprehensive capacity-building program emphasizes two-way, peer-to-peer learning and combines both theory (i.e., interactive lectures led by experts) and practice (i.e., workshops and exercises). Upon completion, participants possess a toolbox of knowledge and skills that can be used to implement sustainable urban planning measures in their cities.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

Storytelling for Participatory Exchange primarily supports steps of the strategic planning cycle that are related to city-level planning and design (Table 7), from the co-design strategies, policies, and spatial interventions (steps 4, 6 and 7) to the implementation of prototypes and upscaling (steps 8 and 10).

Table 7: Strategic activities supported by ISOCARP Trainings for Capacity Building.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	
Engage Stakeholders	
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	x
Evaluate	
Upscale	x

5.3 Liveable Cities Index (Cetaqua)

Description

The Liveable Cities Index (LCI) developed by CETAQUA provides a liveability ranking for cities based on 75 indicators distributed in 5 categories – Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources. It uses publicly available municipal data, thus promoting transparency and accountability and allowing stakeholders to understand how the index is constructed and to trust its findings. The ability to geographically disaggregate the index allows for targeted actions in specific city areas. This can help prioritize interventions in underserved or disadvantaged neighbourhood, promoting a more equitable distribution of resources. Integrating various categories like environmental quality and land use also ensures that the index can reveal inequalities in different dimensions of urban life, from pollution levels to access to green spaces.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

The Liveable Cities Index supports several steps throughout the strategic planning cycle (Table 8). In the early stages (step 1), it provides a comprehensive framework to identify needs and issues based on 5 categories: Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources. The 5-dimensional framework is also useful for feasibility and impact assessment (step 5) and co-designing policies and spatial interventions (steps 6 and 7). In the late stages, it contributes to evaluation and monitoring (step 9) and upscaling (step 10).

Table 8: Strategic activities supported by the Liveable Cities Index.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	x
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	x
Upscale	x

5.4 Learning and Action Alliances (ICATALIST)

Description

The UP2030 Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) developed and coordinated by ICATALIST are local communities of practice focusing on knowledge exchange and co-creation, involving public actors, private actors, users (civil society) and knowledge institutes. These social structures are intended to support communication, coordination, innovation, and dialogue between stakeholders at multiple levels and overcome silo thinking and acting. The fundamental mission of the LAAs is to act as platforms to support the core participatory principles of UP2030: co-production, cross-fertilization, and capacity building. The exchanges within the LAA frame facilitate negotiation and mutual learning among stakeholders, thus reducing conflicts and increasing support and actor buy-in for decisions made. In addition, these participatory activities will help frame questions that are both scientifically and socially relevant. The key outcomes of the LAAs are Partnership Commitments towards climate neutrality in each UP2030 city.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

The Learning and Action Alliances specifically target the step of engaging stakeholders (Table 9) but can be used to support all steps in the cycle.

Table 9: Strategic activities supported by the Learning and Action Alliances.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	
Co-design Interventions	
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	
Upscale	

5.5 Equal Services & Facilities Assessment (LINKS Foundation)

Description

The Equal Services & Facilities Assessment (ES&FA) developed by the LINKS Foundation is a tool to evaluate the spatial distribution of services in relation to the socio-economic characteristics of the population. It helps to identify urban areas and groups that lack access to urban services and facilities. As such, the tool contributes to developing the knowledge base necessary to plan infrastructure changes for an inclusive urban system that addresses the demands of disadvantaged social groups. Similarly, it helps to identify governance tools and processes to empower diverse social groups and increase bottom-up citizen approach.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

The Equal Services & Facilities Assessment supports specific steps in strategic planning (Table 10): the identification of needs (step 1), the co-design of strategies, policies, and spatial interventions (steps 4, 6 and 7), and upscaling (step 10).

Table 10: Strategic activities supported by the Equal Services & Facilities Assessment.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	x
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	
Upscale	x

5.6 Transformative Governance Instruments (Adelphi Research)

Description

Transformative Governance Instruments (TGI) being developed by Adelphi are governance instruments that support cities' transformation to reach their climate-neutrality, social justice and resilience goals. It is being developed entirely within the UP2030 project and focuses on hard and soft policies as well as other governance aspects that allow sector-wide and multi-actor mainstreaming and upscaling of transformation processes. Ultimately, it aims to increase the knowledge of municipal staff of transformative governance and the use of specific governance instruments in support of reaching their goals.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

Transformative Governance Instruments can support strategic steps related to governance (Table 11), including the identification of needs (step 1), the co-design of strategies and policies (steps 4 and 6), and particularly upscaling (step 10).

Table 11: Strategic activities supported by the Transformative Governance Instruments.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	x
Co-design Interventions	
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	
Upscale	x

5.7 City Resilience Framework (RCities)

Description

The City Resilience Framework (CRF) is a conceptual framework developed by RCities offering a reference point to understand resilience in cities from an evidence-based holistic articulation around four categories: (1) People: The health and well-being of everyone living and working in the city; (2) Organization: The systems within the economy and society that enable urban populations to live peacefully, and act collectively; (3) Place: The quality of infrastructure and ecosystems that protect, provide and connect us; and (4) Knowledge: Appropriate leadership and strategy enabling the city to learn from the past and take timely action. The framework has already been used by R-Cities at the city level to support municipalities

worldwide in developing resilience strategies, and in the UP2030 project, the framework is applied at the neighborhood level for the first time.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

As a conceptual framework, the City Resilience Framework mainly supports the early steps of needs identification, stakeholder engagement, co-visioning, and strategy co-design (steps 1-4), as well as the last step of upscaling given its holistic approach.

Table 12: Strategic activities supported by the City Resilience Framework.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	x
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	x
Co-design Strategies	x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	
Co-design Interventions	
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	
Upscale	x

5.8 UP2030 Engagement Toolkit (MfC)

Description

The UP2030 Engagement Toolkit was developed from scratch in the UP2030 project (in WP2) and is described in Deliverable D2.4. The engagement toolkit (ET) contains “tool cards”, which can help city stakeholders plan meaningful engagement activities. The methodologies can be followed to increase engagement capacity among non-experts. The public toolkit is available for any city to make use of. This toolkit has been designed based on the methodology used for the UP2030 project, aiming to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging participatory urban planning and design. It includes a publicly accessible element which comprises the UP2030 process along with the engagement methodologies and approaches used within the project and by partners in previous projects. A dedicated interface is available for UP2030 partners to guide them in the pilots' visioning, action, and upscaling phases.

Analysis

Strategic Planning Cycle

The engagement toolkit specifically targets the step of engaging stakeholders (Table 13).

Table 13: Strategic activities supported by the Engagement Toolkit.

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	
Identify Needs	
Engage Stakeholders	x
Envision Together	
Co-design Strategies	
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	
Co-design Policies	
Co-design Interventions	
Implement and Test Prototypes	
Evaluate	
Upscale	

6 Synthesis: Strategic Planning Cycle Coverage

Table 14 and Table 15 synthesize the analysis of the planning cycle presented in Sections 3 and 4. Table 16 shows the number of tools and approaches for each step of the cycle. These tables show that UP2030 tools for inclusive participation and spatial justice cover all activities within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle.

Concerning the tools within T3.4 (second column in Table 16), high coverage is achieved in steps to identify needs and issues (13 tools and approaches supporting step 1), engage stakeholders (11 supporting step 2), co-design strategies (12 supporting step 4), and co-design policies (10 supporting step 4). A moderate coverage is observed for steps to envision together (6 tools and approaches supporting step 3), co-design interventions (5 supporting step 2), evaluate (7 supporting step 2), and upscale (8 supporting step 2). Finally, low coverage is achieved for steps related to feasibility and impact assessment (1 tool/approach for step 5) and the implementation and testing of prototypes (2 tools and approaches for step 7). When the tools outside T3.4 are considered (third and fourth columns in Table 16), the cycle coverage improves for all steps. Very high coverage is achieved in steps to identify needs and issues (from 13 to 18; step 1), engage stakeholders (from 11 to 15; step 2), co-design strategies (from 12 to 17; step 4), and co-design policies (from 10 to 14; step 6). In particular, higher coverage is achieved for step upscale (from 8 to 14 tools; step 6).

While the moderate coverage for steps to envision together, co-design interventions, and evaluate (steps 3, 7 and 9) present opportunities for improvement, the low coverage of steps related to feasibility and impact assessment and the implementation and testing of prototypes (steps 5 and 8) are explained by the nature of these activities, which are inherently more technical and, thus, more challenging with respect to the engagement of non-technical stakeholders.

Table 14: Coverage of the Planning Cycle – Tools and methodologies within Task 3.4.

	NSM	CM	CYFUD	Spatial Justice Package					
				SJCM	SJR	JRL	SJBT	SJH	CV
Identify Needs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x
Engage Stakeholders	x	x	x		x	x	x		x
Envision Together	x	x	x						x
Co-design Strategies	x	x	x		x	x	x		x
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility									
Co-design Policies		x	x		x	x	x		x
Co-design Interventions		x	x						x
Implement and Test Prototypes			x						
Evaluate	x	x			x	x	x		x
Upscale	x		x	x				x	

Table 15: Coverage of the Planning Cycle – Tools and methodologies outside Task 3.4.

	SfPE	TfCB	LCI	LAAs	ES&FA	TGI	CRF	ET
Identify Needs	x		x		x	x	x	
Engage Stakeholders	x			x			x	x
Envision Together	x						x	
Co-design Strategies	x	x			x	x	x	
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility			x					
Co-design Policies		x	x		x	x		
Co-design Interventions	x	x	x		x			
Implement and Test Prototypes		x						
Evaluate	x		x					
Upscale	x	x	x		x	x	x	

Table 16: Number of tools in each step of the Planning Cycle (within and outside Task 3.4).

Step in the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle	Tools and approaches within Task 3.4	Tools and approaches outside Task 3.4	All tools
Identify Needs	13	5	18
Engage Stakeholders	11	4	15
Envision Together	6	2	8
Co-design Strategies	12	5	17
Evaluate Impact and Feasibility	1	1	2
Co-design Policies	10	4	14
Co-design Interventions	5	4	9
Implement and Test Prototypes	2	1	3
Evaluate	7	2	9
Upscale	8	6	14

7 Dissemination and Education (TUD)

7.1 Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice'

7.1.1 General information

The Symposium “Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design” was a three-day event hosted by TU Delft (Nov 30 in-person, Dec 1 and Dec 5 online, 2023). The symposium was organized by the Centre for the Just City, the Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment at Delft University of Technology, with support from the UP2030 project and the Delft Design for Values Institute (DDFV).

The event featured 127 abstracts from various topics connected to spatial justice, emphasizing the practical application of concepts in various contexts. Key themes included the recognition, distributive, and procedural aspects of spatial justice, encompassing issues like climate justice, mobility justice, participation, and democracy. The event’s diverse range of topics highlighted the multifaceted nature of spatial justice, exploring how different regions and communities experience and address spatial inequalities. The Book of Abstracts can be downloaded from <https://just-city.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/book-abstracts-book-spread.pdf>.

Keynote speakers included:

- Dr Alexandre Frediani, principal researcher at the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED) in London.
- Dr Marielle Feenstra, Senior Researcher on Gender, Innovation and Energy Transition and coordinator at the DDFV Institute, TU Delft.
- Dr Caroline Newton, Associate Professor of Spatial Planning and Strategy and EFL Fellow, TU Delft.
- Professor Behnam Taebi, professor of Energy & Climate Ethics and Scientific Director of the Safety & Security Institute, TU Delft.

The Organizing Committee was composed by:

- Roberto Rocco (TUD) (lead convenor)
- Caroline Newton (TUD) (lead convenor)
- Juliana Gonçalves (TUD) (lead convenor)
- Marcin Dabrowski (TUD)
- Hugo Lopez (TUD)
- Andrés Maglione (University of Naples Federico II)
- Russell Smith (Winston-Salem State University)
- Shahryar Sarabi (University of Eindhoven)

7.1.2 Themes and Keywords

The core concepts and topics shared by all abstracts in the provided document revolve around the following themes:

- Spatial Justice and Urban Planning: Focus on equitable distribution and access to urban spaces, resources, and facilities. Includes analysis of urban development, land use, and the impact of policies on spatial distribution and access.

- Inclusion and Diversity in Urban Spaces: Exploration of gender, socioeconomic, and cultural inclusivity in urban planning. Addresses issues such as women's safety, accessibility for disabled individuals, and the impact of urban design on various social groups.
- Urban Sustainability and Climate Resilience: Discussion on sustainable urban development, climate-resilient design, and environmental justice. Emphasizes the integration of sustainability principles in architecture, urban design, and city planning.
- Community Engagement and Grassroots Movements: Examines the role of community-driven initiatives, local activism, and civic participation in shaping urban spaces and policies. Includes case studies on grassroots efforts to resist privatization and promote spatial justice.
- Globalization, Neoliberalism, and Urban Transformation: Analysis of the impact of global economic forces and neoliberal policies on urban spaces, particularly in developing countries. Explores themes like privatization, gentrification and their effects on local communities.
- Intersectionality and Public Space: Investigates the interplay of multiple social identities (such as gender, race, and class) in shaping experiences of urban public spaces. Focuses on creating inclusive and equitable urban environments.
- Challenges in Urban Accessibility and Mobility: Studies the barriers to accessibility and mobility in urban areas, particularly for vulnerable or marginalized populations. Discusses the design and policy implications for creating more accessible urban environments.

These themes collectively emphasize the importance of equitable, inclusive, and sustainable approaches in urban planning and design, reflecting a holistic understanding of cities' complex social, economic, and environmental dynamics.

7.1.3 Numbers and Geographic Distribution of Participants

The symposium had a total of 32 sessions, divided by thematic axes and the three dimensions of Spatial Justice (Distributive, Procedural and Recognition). 233 abstracts were submitted, and a total of 127 abstracts were accepted (54,5% of abstracts were submitted). 118 abstracts were effectively presented (7% absenteeism). 243 authors from various institutions, from academia, the civic sector, and the private sector, submitted abstracts. In terms of geographical distribution, the numbers are the following:

- Europe: 140 (57.61%) / The Netherlands: 44 (18.11%)
- Asia: 52 (21.40%)
- North America: 24 (9.88%)
- South America: 14 (5.76%)
- Africa: 13 (5.35%)

7.1.4 Publication Plan and Open Access

One noteworthy achievement of the symposium was the publication of the "Symposium Spatial Justice in Practice Book of Abstracts" in Open Access (already available). The symposium has a publication strategy that aims to harvest results in several formats, including:

- a special number in a peer-reviewed journal, namely Planning Practice & Research, collecting the most notable contributions to the symposium (1st semester 2025),
- a handbook with an extensive catalogue and explanation of planning tools that promote dimensions of spatial justice, notably tools for citizen engagement (end 2024),

- an edited book addressing the application of the concept of spatial justice to planning endeavors (post-project).
- a white paper on the main conclusions and recommendations issued from the symposium (end 2024).

7.1.5 [Key Highlights](#)

- **High-Quality Presentations:** The symposium featured presentations of exceptionally high quality, offering valuable insights into the field of spatial justice. Presentations were evaluated through a scoring system that helped define fitness for publication.
- **Interdisciplinary Dialogue:** One of the symposium's standout achievements was its ability to promote interdisciplinary dialogue. Participants engaged in discussions transcending traditional disciplinary boundaries, facilitating a more holistic understanding of spatial justice issues. This was expressed by the consistency of participants in engaging in discussion pre- and post-symposium.
- **Networking Opportunities:** Attendees had ample opportunities for networking and collaboration. This was facilitated by the creation of a mailing list and continuous engagement with participants towards the publication of results.
- **Inclusivity:** The symposium demonstrated a strong commitment to inclusivity, ensuring that diverse voices and perspectives were heard, as attested by the geographical distribution of participants and the variety of participants' backgrounds verified via an enrolment formulary.
- **Global Impact:** The online sessions and open-access publication of abstracts will ensure that the symposium's impact reaches far beyond the event itself. The publication strategy further ensures that this global network will remain active.

7.1.6 [Special Issue on Spatial Justice Tools](#)

The special issue on Spatial Justice Tools gathers insights from the symposium, offering a comprehensive overview of the tools and methods developed. The journal selected was Planning Practice and Research (PPR), which has established itself as the source for current research on planning practice – city and regional, town and country, urban or spatial planning. Citation metrics include:

- 1.6 (2022) Impact Factor
- 1.9 (2022) 5-year IF
- 2.7 (2022) CiteScore (Scopus)

The expected date of publication is the first semester of 2025.

7.1.7 [Policy Brief on Integrating Spatial Justice into Urban Carbon Neutrality](#)

The Policy Brief advocates for a balanced approach to urban planning that incorporates distributive, procedural, and recognition justice, ensuring that climate actions are beneficial and inclusive. Urbanism Policy Briefs are part of an ongoing series published in Open Access by the TU Delft Open Publishing. The expected date of publication is the end of 2024.

8 Conclusion

This report delivers the first version of methodologies and digital resources to promote inclusive participation and spatial justice in urban neutrality transitions. This deliverable combines insights from spatial justice literature (i.e., the three-dimensional framework of distributive, procedural, and recognition justice) and strategic planning (i.e., the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle) to define an integrated framework for inclusive planning and design. This framework is used to systematically describe and assess UP2030 tools and methodologies, indicating how they address the three spatial justice dimensions and where they are placed within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle. As a result, the report provides an overview of how UP2030 resources contribute to inclusive planning and spatial justice and which strategic activities they may support.

While the focus is on the progress within T3.4 “Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice”, the report also includes additional methodologies and resources available within the UP2030 project for inclusive planning and design. In total, the report covered the nine tools and approaches that are part of T3.4 and an additional eight tools that are part of the project that also foster inclusive planning and design. The analysis presented in this report shows that UP2030 tools for inclusive participation and spatial justice cover all activities within the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle. High coverage is achieved in steps to identify needs and issues, engage stakeholders, and co-design strategies and policies. Moderate coverage is observed for steps to envision together, co-design interventions, evaluate, and upscale, while low coverage is achieved for steps related to feasibility and impact assessment and the implementation and testing of prototypes.

In conclusion, the tools, methodologies, and approaches developed in UP2030 constitute a comprehensive collection of resources to transform urban environments into more equitable and just spaces. By recognizing the interconnected dimensions of spatial justice – distributive, procedural, and recognition – and integrating tools and methodologies into a strategic planning cycle, this document aims to support urban planners, policymakers, and designers in integrating spatial justice principles into their strategies for carbon neutrality.

Limitations and next steps

The pilot cities have already identified several UP2030 tools and methods relevant to addressing their needs, including the ones in this report. While interactions between pilot cities and technical partners have already started, the implementation of tools and methods will happen in the action phase. For this reason, the analyses presented in this report are based on the information provided by the project partners concerning the use of their tools/methods in previous cases (for the tools fully developed that need to be contextualized in UP2030 pilot cities) or their intended use and goals (for the tools under development in the project). In the second version of this deliverable, the analyses carried out in this document will be updated based on the implementation of tools and approaches in the pilot cities (for tools within Task 3.4). When relevant, the implementation of other tools and approaches will also be analyzed.

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